

ICT FOR TEACHER IN ADULT EDUCATION

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Introduction :

Adult education is expected to address the socio-economic, cultural, political and environmental problems besieging humanity in their various societies. This is so because adults are the major occupants of the production sectors of the economy. Fasakun (2006) observed that adult education is not concerned with preparing people for life but rather with helping or assisting people (adults) to live more successfully as useful and acceptable members of their societies and contribute meaningfully to the development of those societies. As can be seen from the information above, adult education should be re-positioned to excessively launch the present adults into the orbit where they can respond to the challenges brought in by information and communication technology in order to make meaningful contributions to national development. Nzeneri (2010)

Benefits of ICT in Adult Education :

Kozma (2005) noted that the benefits of ICT in adult education are that ICT can:

1. Offer opportunities for more adult-learner-centred teaching. There is a common belief that the use of ICT in adult education will contribute to more constructivist learning and an increase in activity and greater responsibility of the adult learner (Volman, 2005).
2. Provide the adult educator with new sources of information and knowledge which will enhance the process of and practices of teaching adults. This is because acquisition of ICT knowledge and skills can help the adult educators to obtain basic knowledge of principles of teaching and learning and the skills to apply those principles in teaching – learning situations.
3. Provide adult learners the opportunity for distance learning country-wide with on-line educational materials even in the face of their tight schedule of activities.
4. Help in providing adult-learners with additional resources to assist resource-based learning e.g., the fax, telephone, computers, e-mail, internet, www(World Wide Web) etc.
5. Broaden access to quality educational services for adults at all levels of adult education. 6. Help in producing ICT literate adults who will be useful to themselves and contribute meaningfully to the society in which they belong.

7. Produce adults who are capable of working and participating in the new economies and societies arising from ICT and related development.
8. Help education policy makers in formulating and execution of educational policies which will be inclusive in nature to bridge the gap in education.
9. Widen the range of opportunities for the marginalized and the disadvantaged members in the society by opening access to knowledge.
10. Encourage self-directed learning because adults can engage in personal learning by using their personal computers or internet connection.
11. Help adult learners to have access to tutorial software.
12. Help in improving the effectiveness and efficiency in adult education system in Nigeria as a whole. In addition, adult learners can use ICT in business transactions and other human endeavours activities that require ICT for their accomplishment and achievement of goals.

Limitations of ICT use in Adult Education :

ICT as modern technology that simplifies and facilitates human activities is not only advantageous in many respects but also has many limitations. The limitations can be categorized as adult educators' related, adult learners' related and technology related. All of them potentially limit the benefits of ICT to adult education.

Adult educators' attitude plays an important role in the teaching learning process that utilizes computers and internet connections. Of course, some adult educators may have positive attitudes to the technology, but refrain from using it in teaching due to low self-efficacy, tendency to consider themselves not qualified to teach with technology. In this respect, Ormrod (2006) defined self-efficacy as the extent or strength of one's belief in one's ability to complete tasks and reach goals.

Adult educators' resistance and lack of enthusiasm to use ICT in adult education is also another limitation. Furthermore, many adult educators may not have the required Information and Technology (IT) skills and feel uncomfortable nor do they have trainings needed to use the technology in their teaching. This is a drawback to adult education curriculum enhancement, ICT teaching – learning process and overall academic success of the adult learners and institution. In this era of global technology, adult educators and adult learners are expected to be at least computer literate, adults in the community to be ICT compliant as well as adult learners. People with disabilities should be equipped with assistive technology skill to be able to operate successfully in their communities (Nnazor, 2015).

On the other hand, the limitation of ICT use in adult education is related to adult learners' behaviour. Appropriate use of computer and the internet by adult learners has significant positive effects on adult learners' attitude and their behaviour. Learners tend to misuse the technology for leisure time activities and have less time to learn and study. Yousef and Dahamani (2008) described online gaming, use of face book, chat rooms and other communication channels as perceived draw backs of ICT use in adult education because learners easily switch to these sites at the expense of their study. Internet access at

home for instance, may be a distraction because of chat rooms and online games, reducing the time spent in learning (Kulik, 1994). For example, while adult learners use the internet, it may confuse them by the multiplicity of information to choose from. As a result, the adult educator spends much time to control them from website unrelated to the learning content.

The other limitation of ICT use in adult education is technology related. The high cost of technology and maintenance of facilities, high cost of spare parts, virus attacks of software and the computer, interruptions of internet connections and poor supply of electric power are among the technology related limitations of ICTs use in adult education.

Challenges of ICT integration in Adult Education :

The integration of ICT in adult education may face various challenges with respect to policy, planning, infrastructure, learning content and language, capacity-building and financing (Fasakun, 2006). ICT – enhanced adult education requires clearly stated objectives for mobilization of resources and political commitment of the concerned bodies (Igbo, 2008). Other challenges of the level of policy and planning are identification of stakeholders and harmonization of efforts across different interest groups, the piloting of the chosen ICT – based model, and specification of existing sources of financing and the development of strategies for generating financial resources to support ICT use over a long term. The infrastructural challenges that may exist are absence of appropriate buildings and rooms to house the technology, lack of/and epileptic power supply, and continuous disruptions in telephone lines. With respect to challenges of capacity building, adult educators lack professional training facilities for them to be ICT skilled and computer literate. In fact, one impeding factor of ICT integration in adult education is the skill gap of the people implementing it (Nnazor, 2005). For instance, adult educators need professional development to gain skills with particular applications of ICT integration into existing curricula, curricula changes related to ICT use, changes in adult educators roles and on underpinning adult educational theories such as adult learners-centred learning. Furthermore, learning contents and language also pose challenge to integration of ICT in adult education. Content development is a critical area that educators overlook (Ibeh, 2008). In integrating ICT in adult education, we have to take cognisance of the relevance of the learning content to the target groups. With respect to language, English is the dominant language in the developing countries, and this is one barrier in the integration of ICT to adult education. Another great challenge is that financing ICT in adult education programmes requires large capital investment. Most adult education centres especially in the rural areas are not equipped with ICT gadgets and tools, computers, internet facilities, assistive technologies like Braille for the virtually improved, mobile wheel chairs for the handicapped adults, among others as a result of huge capital involve

ICT and Lifelong Learning:

- o From face-to-face, to blended and online mode of learning
- o Opens up new possibilities for adults, as learning can be flexible:

- ∪ at any time, any place, and at any pace
- ∪ Learning can be modular with ICT – learners can study materials in and sequence they prefer
- ∪ Learning is more customized, as each learner can appropriate it to their own needs
- ∪ With ICT, learners can search for new content, in addition to the course
- ∪ The instructor is the facilitator and not the source of all knowledge.

Problems that Adult Learners Face :

- ∪ Scheduling
- ∪ Lack of time
- ∪ Family and professional responsibilities
- ∪ Lack of money
- ∪ Mobility problems

Principles of Andragogy:

1. Adults need to be involved in the planning and evaluation of their instruction.
2. Experience (including mistakes) provides the basis for the learning activities.
3. Adults are most interested in learning subjects that have immediate relevance and impact to their job or personal life.
4. Adult learning is problem-centered rather than content-oriented.

Designing Learning for Adult Learners:

Adult Principles and Characteristics

- Need for practical Learning that focuses on problems and goals and that is useful for real life problems.
- Feedback for development
- Personal learning styles
- Collaboration and reciprocity
- Different motivations for learning
- Adult bring their own learning

Designing Learning

- . Urge your learners to identify what they would need to learn.
- . Provide clear and Smart objectives.
- . Provides examples and cases.
- . Demonstrate applications of knowledge and connections to real life.
- . Opportunities for immediate Feedback.
- . Provide opportunities for self Evaluation.
- . Highlight new improvements.
- . Use different methods and models (e.g. auditory ,visual)
- . Allow Learning based on learners' preferences.
- . Create team-based activities.
- . Connect Learning with learners' Motivation.
- . Activities for reflection

- Knowledge and experiences to class.
 - They learn better if they can be Associated with the new information and skills
 - Self- directed and autonomous learning
 - Adult need their knowledge and Experiences acknowledged and Appreciated.
- . Activities based on learners' Experiences.
 - . Activities that extend already known information.
 - . Appropriate learning to adult learner needs and goals.
 - . Establish objectives with adult learners
 - . Provide templates and useful tools
 - . As learners to explore and inquire
 - . Facilitate group discussions
 - . Do not expose your learners through activities.
 - . Create activities for sharing Experiences and knowledge.
 - . Be flexible in the course
 - . Welcome any Questions, doubts, or anxieties.

Conclusion:

From the foregoing, it is evident that ICT empowers citizens to continuously adapt to community, national and global developmental challenges, as well as to develop the required knowledge, skills associated with life-long learning and community development. This is, therefore, a challenge to literacy, and special education instructors in Nigeria. There is need for the appropriate integration of ICT in adult education settings to enhance the capacity of both adult educators and adult learners to become more responsive to new challenges in ICT. Integrating ICT in adult education programmes would provide everyone with basic skills and to use such new technologies during development training, workshop, seminars, conference, teaching and learning environment.

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